

The high molecular weight complex formed by the plant immune receptor Rx does not contain host protein RanGAP2

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Abstract

This Technical Note complements our paper on the activation of sensor-helper paired NLRs in the solanaceous NRC network (Contreras *et al.*, 2022). The NLR protein Rx (confers virus resistance) constitutively forms a high molecular weight complex that is independent of its downstream helpers of the NLR required for cell death (NRC) family. Here, we show that RanGAP2, a previously identified interactor of Rx does not form part of this immune complex under our assay conditions. The exact nature of the Rx high molecular weight complex therefore remains elusive.

Background

In the main study that this Technical Note accompanies (Contreras *et al.*, 2022), we leveraged the Rx-NRC paired NLR system to gain mechanistic insights of paired sensor-helper activation in the NRC immune receptor network. Rx is a well-characterized disease resistance protein that confers resistance to *Potato Virus X* (PVX) by recognizing its coat protein (CP) (Bendahmane *et al.*, 1999). To confer virus resistance, Rx genetically requires downstream helper NLRs, NRC2, NRC3 or NRC4 (Derevnina *et al.*, 2021; Wu *et al.*, 2017). We used transient expression in *Nicotiana benthamiana* coupled with BN-PAGE to study how Rx and NRC2 activate upon CP perception.

We showed that Rx mediates oligomerization of its downstream helper NLRs, NRC2 and NRC4, into higher-order oligomeric complexes that do not include Rx (Contreras *et al.*, 2022). Interestingly, in these BN-PAGE assays we also observed that Rx constitutively forms high molecular weight complexes of around 400 kDa. These complexes do not exhibit any change in size upon Rx activation and are independent of the presence of downstream helper NRCs. Such high molecular weight complexes were not observed in BN-PAGE assays with other inactive NRC-dependent sensor NLRs such as Rpi-amr1 and Rpi-amr3 (Ahn *et al.*, 2022).

As monomeric Rx is around 115 kDa, we speculated that this complex could be either a pre-formed Rx homo-oligomer or a complex formed by Rx and other endogenous host proteins. Rx has previously been shown to associate with RanGAP2 (Tameling & Baulcombe, 2007), with Rx-RanGAP2 association having been shown to be required for PVX resistance (Tameling & Baulcombe, 2007). This led us to hypothesize that this constitutive Rx-specific complex could include RanGAP2.

Results

In this study, we attempted to test this hypothesis. To this end, we generated C-terminally tagged RanGAP2 variants and attempted to visualize an *in vivo* Rx-RanGAP2 complex. We co-expressed C-terminally 6xHA-tagged Rx and C-terminally 4xMyc-tagged NRC2 together with a C-terminally V5-tagged version of RanGAP2 and performed BN-PAGE assays as described previously (Contreras *et al.*, 2022). As in our main study, we used a variant of NRC2 with mutations in its N-terminus which abolish cell death while maintaining the capacity to activate and oligomerize (NRC2^{EEE}) and carried out all assays by transient overexpression in leaves of *nrc2/3/4* *N. benthamiana* CRISPR mutants (Adachi *et al.*, 2019; Contreras *et al.*, 2022).

As reported previously, Rx migrates at ~400 kDa and does not exhibit any change in size upon activation with PVX CP. RanGAP2 accumulates to high levels and is visualized primarily as a band of ~160 kDa. We also observed a fainter higher molecular weight band migrating at a size of ~700kDa (**Figure 1**). We were unable to detect any obvious signal for RanGAP2 co-migrating with Rx. This indicates that the Rx complex does not include RanGAP2. CP migrates as a high molecular weight complex of ~500 kDa indicative of *in planta* oligomerization (**Figure 1**). CP did not co-migrate with Rx or RanGAP2, which is in line with previous literature (Tameling *et al.* 2007), in which CP was shown not to form a stable complex with Rx or RanGAP2 pointing towards an indirect mechanism of recognition.

Figure 1: Rx, RanGAP2 and CP do not co-migrate in BN-PAGE assays.

BN-PAGE and SDS-PAGE assays with inactive and activated Rx-NRC2. C-terminally 6xHA tagged Rx, C-terminally 4xMyc-tagged NRC2^{EEE} and C-terminally V5-tagged RanGAP2 were co-expressed with either free GFP or C-terminally GFP-tagged CP. Total protein extracts were run on native and denaturing PAGE assays in parallel and immunoblotted with the appropriate antisera labelled on the left. Approximate molecular weights (kDa) of the proteins are shown on the right. Rubisco loading control was carried out using Ponceau stain (PS).

Conclusions

The lack of co-migration between Rx and RanGAP2 in our BN-PAGE assays suggests that the association identified by co-immunoprecipitation by Tamelung *et al.* (2007) potentially exists in low abundance and is therefore not visualized under the conditions of our assays. Perhaps only a small pool of the total RanGAP2 interacts with Rx which is masked by higher abundance of forms migrating at other MWs. It is also possible that the V5 epitope is hidden when RanGAP2 is in complex with Rx. Nonetheless, we currently have no evidence supporting the hypothesis that the 400 kDa Rx complex includes RanGAP2. The precise nature of this Rx complex remains to be determined.

Materials and Methods

Plant growth conditions

nrc2/3/4 CRISPR mutant *N. benthamiana* lines were grown in a controlled environment growth chamber with a temperature range of 22 to 25 °C, humidity of 45% to 65% and a 16/8-hour light/dark cycle.

Plasmid constructions

The Golden Gate Modular Cloning (MoClo) kit (Weber *et al.*, 2011) and the MoClo plant parts kit (Engler *et al.*, 2014) were used for cloning, and all vectors are from this kit unless specified otherwise. CP, Rx, and NRC2^{EEE} were cloned into the binary vector pJK268c, which contains the Tomato bushy stunt virus silencing inhibitor p19 in the backbone (Kourelis *et al.*, 2020). RanGAP2 was cloned into the pICH86988 vector. Cloning design and sequence analysis were done using Geneious Prime (v2021.2.2; <https://www.geneious.com>).

Extraction of total proteins for BN-PAGE and SDS-PAGE assays

Four to five-week-old plants were agroinfiltrated as described above with constructs of interest and leaf tissue was collected 3 days post agroinfiltration. Final OD₆₀₀ used was 0.3 for Rx and NRC2 immune receptors, 0.2 for GFP and CP and 0.1 for RanGAP2. BN-PAGE was performed using the Bis-Tris Native PAGE system (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Leaf tissue was ground using a Geno/Grinder tissue homogenizer and total protein was subsequently extracted and homogenized extraction buffer. GTMN extraction buffer was used (10% glycerol, 50 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 5 mM MgCl₂ and 50 mM NaCl) supplemented with 10 mM DTT, 1x protease inhibitor cocktail (SIGMA) and 0.2% Nonidet P-40 Substitute (SIGMA). Samples were incubated in extraction buffer on ice for 10 minutes with short vortex mixing every 2 minutes. Following incubation, samples were centrifuged at 5,000 *xg* for 15 minutes and the supernatant was used for BN-PAGE and SDS-PAGE assays.

BN-PAGE assays

For BN-PAGE, samples extracted as detailed above were diluted as per the manufacturer's instructions by adding NativePAGE 5% G-250 sample additive, 4x Sample Buffer and water. After dilution, samples were loaded and run on Native PAGE 3%-12% Bis-Tris gels alongside either NativeMark unstained protein standard (Invitrogen) or SERVA Native Marker (SERVA). The proteins were then transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride membranes using NuPAGE Transfer Buffer using a Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (Bio-Rad) as per the manufacturer's instructions. Proteins were fixed to the membranes by incubating with 8% acetic acid for 15 minutes, washed

with water and left to dry. Membranes were subsequently re-activated with methanol in order to correctly visualize the unstained native protein marker. Membranes were immunoblotted as described below.

SDS-PAGE assays

For SDS-PAGE, samples were diluted in SDS loading dye and denatured at 72 °C for 10 minutes. Denatured samples were spun down at 5,000 $\times g$ for 3 minutes and supernatant was run on 4%-20% Bio-Rad Mini-PROTEAN TGX gels alongside a PageRuler Plus prestained protein ladder (Thermo Scientific). The proteins were then transferred to polyvinylidene difluoride membranes using Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer Buffer using a Trans-Blot Turbo Transfer System (Bio-Rad) as per the manufacturer's instructions. Membranes were immunoblotted as described below.

Immunoblotting and detection of BN-PAGE and SDS-PAGE assays

Blotted membranes were blocked with 5% milk in Tris-buffered saline plus 0.01% Tween 20 (TBS-T) for an hour at room temperature and subsequently incubated with desired antibodies at 4 °C overnight. Antibodies used were anti-GFP (B-2) HRP (Santa Cruz Biotechnology), anti-HA (3F10) HRP (Roche), anti-Myc (9E10) HRP (Roche), and anti-V5 (V2260) HRP (Roche), all used in a 1:5000 dilution in 5% milk in TBS-T. To visualize proteins, we used Pierce ECL Western (32106, Thermo Fisher Scientific), supplementing with up to 50% SuperSignal West Femto Maximum Sensitivity Substrate (34095, Thermo Fishes Scientific) when necessary. Membrane imaging was carried out with an ImageQuant 800 luminescent imager (GE Healthcare Life Sciences, Piscataway, NJ). Rubisco loading control was stained using Ponceau S (Sigma).

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